

(commercial grade, 96%) for 30 min increased germination to more than 90%. Seeds must be washed very quickly after treatment so as not to subject them to temperatures of more than 45 °C. Slow washing resulted in temperatures of about 110 °C that damaged seeds and resulted in very poor germination. Diluting commercial grade H₂SO₄ tenfold was not effective. □

Flowering, seed production, and germination of *Sesbania speciosa* used as green manure for lowland rice in Sri Lanka

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We evaluated the flowering, seed production, and germination of *S. speciosa* for use in a green manuring system for lowland rice in Sri Lanka.

The study was conducted in the ARS lowland experimental site at Maha Illuppallama, in the dry zone, Sri Lanka. Soil is Tropaqualf with pH of about 7.3, 4.4% organic matter, 0.095% total N, and 94 µg available P/g soil. We conducted a

year-round *S. speciosa* planting trial from Nov 1990 to Oct 1991.

During the first week of each month, we seeded a 5- × 4-m plot with *S. speciosa* at 0.05- × 0.5-m row spacing. Plots were irrigated once every 3 d and kept weed-free. We recorded dates of 50% flowering in the plots (a visual observation), podding, and seed setting.

Because seed germination can be as low as 30%, we applied two promising seed treatments—concentrated sulfuric acid for 40 min and 80°C water for 45 s—to improve germination in wet-sand cultures.

Monthly seeding of *S. speciosa* resulted in irregular flowering (see figure) and seed production. Seeding between Jan and Mar produced 5.6–8.5 g seed/plant; Apr–Aug, 12.1–15.5 g seed/plant; and Sep to Dec, 4.7, 4.4, 2.0, and 0.9 g seed/plant, respectively.

Seeding *S. speciosa* between May and Oct causes it to flower during Nov–Dec (see figure) and to pod and set seed in Jan–Feb. This schedule is the most efficient for

The effect of seed treatment on germination of *S. speciosa*.

Seed treatment	Germination ^a (%)
Acid	61 ± 5a
Hot water	35 ± 5 b
Control	20 ± 4 c

^a Germination (%) ± SE. Values followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level according to *x*²-test.

Effect of monthly daylength on flowering of *S. speciosa*. Circle that crosses the shaded sectors indicates 12 h photoperiod.

seed production because it concentrates seed setting into a period as short as 2 mo. Because *S. speciosa* is photoperiod sensitive, this seed production program is useful for tropical countries with similar monthly daylengths.

The acid treatment enhanced germination of *S. speciosa* significantly compared with the hot water treatment, which was significantly better than the control (see table). □

Ammonia excretion by *Anabaena azollae* immobilized in alginate and its effect on the growth of rice seedlings

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Azolla is a water fern that fixes atmospheric N in association with an algal symbiont. *A. azollae* can contribute 40–60 kg N/ha of a rice crop under low-cost rice production management.

We investigated the effect of immobilizing two strains of algal

1. Algal symbiont AS-K₄ immobilized in calcium alginate.